

IMPACT OF TRANSFORMATIONAL AND TRANSACTIONAL LEADERSHIP STYLES ON CHANGE AT SELECTED AUTOMOBILE DEALERSHIPS IN DURBAN, SOUTH AFRICA

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ABSTRACT

Leadership effectiveness is a major area of concern in a political, social and organizational context (Park, 2021:1-22). Leadership is a core component of organizational management, but its functions are getting more complex with the increasing involvement of changes taking place in the world (Sung & kim, 2021). As such, the complicated operation of managing resistance to change amongst employees is very critical. Resistance to change, on the other hand, is described as one of the impediments to organizational expansion due to its negative consequences. To cope with change, there is a need for an effective leadership style (Moradi, Jefari, Doorbash & Mirzaei, 2021:171-179, Malhotra, Zietsma, Morris & Smets, 2021:475-520). This study focuses on organizational change and associated leadership styles, i.e., transformational and transactional leadership styles as an embodiment of other leadership styles. The study further seeks to investigate the impact of these leadership styles on employee resistance to change at the selected automobile dealerships in the Durban Metropolitan Region of KwaZulu-Natal in South Africa. Theories on change and leadership styles have been considered in this paper. A descriptive survey design was adopted to collect information from a stratified sample size using self-administered questionnaires to 170 staff at automotive dealerships in the metropolitan of Durban in South Africa. Pearson correlational and regression analysis were employed to analyze data. Results indicated significant correlations between these leadership styles and resistance to change. However, the transactional leadership style revealed a stronger possibility of increasing resistance to change. The study recommends that management should practice the transformational leadership style with a view to encouraging employee participation in the decision, building confidence, accepting constructive criticisms, effective communication and transparency.

1. INTRODUCTION

The body of literature built around change management widely accepts the detrimental effects of employee resistance to change (Men, Yue & Liu, 2020:101; Oreg & Berson, 2019:272-307). In combatting this resistance, various strategies have been proposed and one of the most pertinent revolves around strong leadership within the change process (Mansaray, 2019:18-31; Jones, Hutcheson & Camba, 2021:936-948).

Change leadership styles may function as change agents for strategic planning implementation by creating a vision, identifying the need for change and implementing the change itself (Galli, 2018:124-132). Herein, previous research (Caulified and Senger, 2017; Ausick, 2014; Gibbons, 2015; Dumons, 2008; Mc Grati, 2015, Shondrick and Lord, 2010; and Baker, 2007) has demonstrated the statistical association between these leadership styles and employee resistance to change. Still, these previous studies have not fully explored the transformational leadership style and its impacts on organizational change management and alleviating employee resistance tendencies (Gibson, 2015; Dung & Hai, 2020:6)

This study focuses on transformational and transactional leadership styles of change leadership as they both encapsulate the various components of change leadership styles in existence. Emery and Baker (2012) review of the relationship between both change leadership styles and employee resistance to change detected that employees managed under transformational leadership styles displayed higher job satisfaction and commitment to change compared to employees managed under transactional leadership style (Peng, Li, Wang & Lin, 2021:369-397). This notion has been further supported by modern-day scholars suggesting that transformational leadership paves way for easy communication between employees and their managers or leaders, increase motivation and satisfaction level of employees and most importantly, prepares their minds to be more innovative and receptive toward technological advancement (Islam, Furuoka & Idris, 2021:95-102, Peng, Li, Wang & Lin, 2021:369-397). Whereas, transactional leadership emphasizes the practice of rewards and punishments for efficient staff performance. This practice of leadership has over time, proved to be very threatening and intimidating to some employees who struggle with change adaptation, their cognitive abilities, values and beliefs (Atasoy, 2020:256-274; Islam, Furuoka & Idris, 2021:95-102).

In general, research investigation by various scholars regarding these change leadership styles agree that organisations can successfully adapt to change when the leaders or managers of an organization encourage employee participation, effective communication and transparency (Atasoy, 2020:256-274; Islam, Furuoka & Idris, 2021:95-102).

The study seeks to emphasize the need for organizations to focus rather on the transformational leadership style which encourages employee participation, effective communication and transparency (Atasoy, 2020:256-274; Islam, Furuoka & Idris, 2021:95-102).

The study further seeks to investigate the impact of these change leadership styles on resistance to change at the selected automobile dealerships in the Durban Metropolitan Region of KwaZulu-Natal Province in South Africa. A survey of 170 staff was conducted with the

administration of questionnaires. The Multi-Leadership Questionnaire (M.L.Q) and Resistance to Change Questionnaire by Oreg (2006) were adapted to investigate the behaviours of employees towards change leadership and how it impacted their resistance levels. Hypothesis generated were tested by means of correlational analysis which was employed to investigate the relationship between these constructs.

Accordingly, the aim of the study is

To investigate the effect of change Transformational and Transactional Leadership styles on cognitive rigidity as a determinant of employees' change resistance.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Back Ground of the South African Automotive Industry

The South African automotive industry makes an important contribution to the South African economy (Sutherland, 2020:233-252). However, the NAAMSA report (2016), indicates that the major challenge in the South African Automobile industry relates to adopting and sustaining new technological changes. According to Maisiri, Van Dyk & Coetzee, (2021:1013), these challenges include artificial intelligence on the part of the management which can only be necessitated with the appropriate leadership skills and successful change management in the industry.

These challenges have affected the automotive dealership companies by causing pressure on price and delivery times, quality and overall customer service improvements, and environmentally friendly products with the rapid introduction of new products (National Automotive Dealership Association reports, 2015). Added to this, is the greatest challenge faced by the South African Automotive Industry involving leadership management skills resulting in negative implications on its performance (Gonyora, Migiro, Mashau & Ngwenya, 2022:1139-1148). Poor management expertise in the South African Automotive Industry has also resulted in poor commitment and involvement of its workers (Moos & Sambo, 2018:467-494). This study seeks to focus on the impact of transformational and transactional leadership management on employee resistance at selected dealership companies in the Durban Metropolitan Region of KwaZulu-Natal in South Africa.

2.2 Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework of this paper is based on the contention that transformational and transactional leadership styles play a significant role in affecting the cognitive rigidity of employees' resistance to change which will be considered in this study. These leadership styles become prominent in eventually determining the successful management of an organization as well as the efficacy of employee work performance. For this reason, an overview of transformational leadership theory, transactional leadership theory and cognitive rigidity as a dimension of resistance to change theory will be discussed.

Overview of Transformational leadership style

Jensen, Andersen & Jacobsen (2019:12-24) posited that Transformational leadership is required in an organization where patterns of actions include behaviors such as clarifying goals, communicating, taking consistent actions, caring, and creating opportunities for development. While Egli (2019:38) argues that transformational leadership enhance the motivation, morale, and performance of followers through a variety of mechanisms. On the other hand, Wonacott (2012) captures four factors which motivate employees to perform beyond expectations. These factors have further been explored by other authors with regard to transformational leadership style. They have also been considered for the purpose of this study and are as follows:

Idealised influence: The degree to which the leaders behave in admirable ways and display conviction by taking stands (Oginde, 2020:65-74; Muppidathi & Krishnan, 2021:269-285).

Inspirational motivation: The degree to which the leader articulates a vision that appeals to and inspires the followers with optimism about future goals and offers meaning for the current tasks in hand (Collins, Stephen & Chiamaka, 2020:37-43).

Intellectual stimulation: The degree to which the leader challenges assumptions, and stimulates and encourages creativity in the followers by providing a framework for followers to see how they connect to the leader, the organization, and each other and creatively overcome any obstacle (Ma & Jiang, 2018:302-324).

Idealised consideration: The degree to which the leader attends to each individual follower's needs and acts as a mentor or coach and gives respect to and appreciation of the individual's contributions. This fulfils and enhances each individual team member's need for self-fulfilment and self-worth (Khair, 2021:79-85; Mbindyo, O'Connor & Nandedkar, 2021:12).

These factors are promoted and put into effect by transformational leaders who develop, intellectually inspire, and inspire them to work towards a collective purpose, vision, or mission. The common factor in all four of the motivating factors of employees is their leader. Because of this, transformational leadership has the potential to be a dynamic force in an organization and is vital to increasing efficiency and employee work performance.

Overview of Transactional Leadership style

Transactional leadership focuses on the role of supervision, organization and group performance (Lee & Ding, 2020:668-681). Kubai, Gachunga & Odhiambo (2022) added that transactional leadership is a style of leadership in which the leader promotes compliance of his followers through rewards or punishments. On the contrary, Dasborough and Scandura (2022:219-223) argue that the transactional leadership style is a "hands-off" approach to employees and as such, leaders do not take stands on issues.

Oyerinde (2020:79-94) further supports the notion that transactional leaders do not emphasize results, do not take action when issues arise and are very unaware of employee performance. Several other scholars also agree that the transactional leadership style only takes corrective actions and only stresses what people are doing wrong, as they make it a point to enforce rules,

disliking any change in the status quo (Jowah 2020; Venet, 2021; Malodia, Kaur, Ractham, Sakashita & Dhir (2022:605-618; Hodson, 2021:932-955). In general,

Based on the above depictions of transactional leadership, it can be assumed that this leadership style could cause fear and mistrust of management among employees, thereby fostering a stressful environment which is not conducive to change.

For the purpose of this study, certain factors found by Burns (1978:23) were considered for further investigations. These factors are as follows and were further explored by other authors.

Contingent reward: A form of praise given when the set of goals is accomplished on time, ahead of time or to keep subordinates working at a good pace at different times throughout completion (Hussein, Ibrahim & Ismael, 2022:46-60)

Active Management by Exception: This leadership form means that the leader continually looks at each subordinate's performance and makes changes to the subordinate's work and makes corrections throughout the whole process (Francisco, 2019:622-635)

Passive Management by Exception: Leaders wait for issues to come up before fixing the problems (Ugwu & Okore, 2020:864-879)

In summary, several authors of the transactional leadership theory, agree that this form of leadership style pursues a cost-benefit, economic change to meet subordinates' current and material and physical needs in return for "contracted" services rendered by subordinates (Hahim, 2019; Irungu, 2021; Vayre, 2022). Whereas, transformational leadership scholars generally agree that an existing need or demand of a potential follower looks for potential motives in followers, seeks to satisfy higher needs, and engages the follower (Seitz & Owens, 2021:95-109; Colman & Lion, 2021:1-20; Pradhan & Jena, 2019:30-40). This implies that the transactional leader works with the organizational culture as it exists, while the transformational leader changes the organizational culture.

Overview of Resistance to Change

The concept of "resistance to change" simply refers to a natural reaction of employees to a new change process (Yue, Men & Ferguson, 2019:101779). Change is uncomfortable and requires new ways of thinking and doing things which makes people have trouble developing a vision of what life will look like with change (Barak, 2018:115-123).

According to Barak (2018:115-123), the first essential step in the change process is for management to ensure that there is enough motivation and preparation for the upcoming change (Stouten, Rousseau & De Cremer, 2018:752-788). In the context of organizational change, resistance is frequently presented and perceived as irrational and problematical, something that needs to be dealt with in any change management initiative and has many definitions. Mansaray (2019:18-31) describes resistance as "an ongoing problem for change managers" and Jakubowicz, (2020:28-48) believes that the problem of resistance "lies at the heart of most change programs".

Organisations perceive change as very important for their survival and prosperity in today's more competitive environment and new business challenges. They make change initiatives to keep up the pace with the ever-changing and competitive environment (Kunz, 2021:22-37). The success and performance superiority of an organisation is very much dependent on its ability to align its internal functional structure with external demands (Li, Chen, Yi, Mao & Liao, 2019:1448-1463). The current economic crisis in the automotive industry reveals that a reactive attitude of companies is not enough (Martins & Kaminski, 2019:1684806). This implies that there is a need to be proactive and implement change continuously.

Stouten, Rousseau & De Cremer (2018:752-788) claim that "organisational change can generate scepticism and resistance in employees, making it sometimes difficult or impossible to implement organisational improvements. Overcoming resistance to change has been discussed and investigated by several scholars for many decades, and even today, the problem is still topical due to rapid technological advances and a fiercely competitive landscape, as organizational changes are required to stay competitive (Yao, Zhou, Liu, Xu, Chen, Wang & Shao, 2020:193; Ahmed, Khalil & Hilal, 2021:115183; Moradi, Jefari, Doorbash & Mirzaei, 2021:171-179).

Resistance affects the speed at which an innovation is adopted, and this affects the feelings and opinions of employees at all stages of the adoption process. This is because resistance to change can intensify if employees feel that they have been involved in a series of changes without enough support (Chiu, Zhu & Corbett, 2021:102379).

In today's turbulent times, mastering innovation is a competitive necessity because it contributes tremendously to the organisation (Ekot, 2021:58-69). Alzoubi & Aziz (2021:130) further suggested that to make innovation visible, the management needs to set a platform to accommodate the changes.

You, Kim & Lim (2021:723-741) further argue that leaders or managers might fail to overcome resistance to change, but it can be well managed. If management does not understand, accept and try to break resistance barriers, even the most well-intentioned and well-conceived change efforts can go wrong. Newbould, Tucker & Wilberforce (2022:128-130) state "any management's ability to achieve maximum benefit from change depends on how effectively they create and maintain a climate that minimizes resistance behaviour and encourages acceptance and support.

2.3 The Effect of Transformational vs Transactional Leadership on Employee Resistance to Change

Previous findings from studies support that there is a significant relationship between transformational leadership and employee resistance to change (H1) (Newbould, Tucker & Wilberforce (2022:126-130). However, Nielsen et al. (2008:468) reveal that transformational leadership was positively related to better working conditions. Prosci's model of change management also suggests that good working leads to increased commitment to work.

Transactional leadership, on the other hand, displays behaviours intended to prevent potential problems before they arise, and this could also help curb resistance to change knowing their expected deliveries of a task are over-inspected to prevent failures (Iscan, Ersari and Natiyok, 2014: 882). Findings from Iscan et al. (2014:882) reveal that leadership based on searching for mistakes poses a threat to the fulfilment of autonomy needs as it reduces the number of freedom employees has which invariably inhibits employee resistance to change. Additionally, excessive controlling behavior by leaders can undermine a follower's sense of self-achievement at work. Emery and Baker (2008:84) also claim there is a significant correlation between transactional leadership and employee resistance to change (Hypothesis 2) especially when the leaders apply a wrong or inappropriate change management approach.

2.4 Cognitive Rigidity as a Dimension of Resistance to Change

A multidimensional view of resistance posited that negative responses to change are expressed along distinct dimensions (Stevens, Acic & Taylor, 2021; 815-821). Based on Piderit's (2009) conceptualization of resistance, Oreg (2003) conducted an explanatory factor analysis of resistance to change and reported four factors describing an individual's predisposition to resist change which are as follows:

- Routine seeking
- Emotional reaction
- Short term focus
- Cognitive rigidity

For the purpose of this study, cognitive rigidity as a determinant of employee resistance to change will be carefully investigated. Cognitive rigidity is an antecedent of resistance to change and refers to employees' thoughts and beliefs about change (Oreg, 2009). Oreg & Syerdlik (2018:327-352) stated that what one thinks and believes about change can be thought of as the ability of an individual to alter their beliefs in order to respond to change. Cognitive rigidity addresses the ease and frequency with which individuals change their attitudes and conform to change. Differences in cognitive dispositions can be discussed through issues such as cognitive complexity, authoritarianism and dogmatism, and emotional intelligence (Daly, 2002). In relation to the resistance to change, dogmatic individuals are rigid and closed-minded. A highly dogmatic person might be less open to new circumstances and change.

Oreg's study also found a relationship between leadership and cognitive rigidity as a determinant of employee dispositional resistance to change. Specially, a lower level of trust in management was related to a higher level of affective, cognitive, and behavioural resistance. With respect to the amount of information about the change, a relationship was found between behaviour and cognitive resistance, but not effective resistance. However, Warnberg and Banas (2000:132) reported that more information about change led to a worse evaluation of it and finally provoked a willingness to resist it. Oreg explained this finding by arguing that resistance to change appears without any good reasons and is due to employees' unfamiliarity with the new contents of work.

Resistance to change is related to readiness for change. Readiness is to want it cognitively while resistance is not to accept or want it. People do not like change if they are intimidated or their beliefs, values and behaviours are threatened. For this reason, it is important to determine the leadership style practiced for organisational change and managing resistance in every organisation.

2.5 Conceptual Framework and Hypothetical Development

This research aims to examine the impact of transactional and transformational leadership styles on cognitive rigidity as a dimension of resistance to change. By studying the theoretical and empirical literature, the following hypothesis was formulated and tested using the data collection tools.

H1: Transformational Leadership has an impact on cognitive rigidity

H1a: Idealised influence has an impact on cognitive rigidity

H1b: Intellectual stimulation has an impact on cognitive rigidity

H1c: Inspirational motivation has an impact on cognitive rigidity

H1d: Idealised consideration has an impact on cognitive rigidity

H2: Transactional Leadership style has an impact on cognitive rigidity

H2a: Active management by exception has an impact on cognitive rigidity.

H2b: Passive management by exception has an impact on cognitive rigidity.

H2c: Contingent reward has an impact on cognitive rigidity.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

H1: Transformational Leadership has an impact on cognitive rigidity as a dimension of employee resistance to change

Previous findings from studies support that a significant relationship exists between transformational leadership and resistance to change (Hypothesis 1). Nielsen et al. (2008:468) revealed that transformational leadership was positively associated with better working conditions. Prosci's model of change management also suggests that good working conditions lead to increased commitment to work.

H2: Transactional Leadership style has an impact on cognitive rigidity as a dimension of employee resistance to change

According to Iscan, Ersari and Natiyok (2014:882), "leader's display behaviors intended to prevent potential problems before they arise, and this could cause fear of being reprimanded for non-compliance. This could also help curb resistance to change knowing their expected deliveries of the task are over-inspected to prevent failures".

Findings from the study conducted by Iscan et al. (2014:882), reveal that leadership based on searching for mistakes poses a threat to the fulfilment of autonomy needs as it reduces the amount of freedom employees have which invariably inhibits employee resistance. Additionally, excessive controlling behavior by the leader can undermine a follower's sense of self-achievement at work. Emery and Baker (2008:84) also claim there is a significant correlation between transactional leadership and resistance to change (Hypothesis 2) especially when the leader utilizes a wrong change management approach.

Findings from this study reveal a linear relationship between resistance to change and transactional leadership in the surveyed companies which shows a negative correlation ($r=0.365$) suggesting that as resistance to change increases, transactional leadership increases and vice versa. This correlation value is less than that of the transformational leadership style which implies that the transactional leadership style stands a better chance to increase resistance to change compared to the transformational leadership style just as suggested by other research findings.

3. RESEARCH METHODS

The study investigates the relationship between transformational and transactional leadership styles on cognitive rigidity as a determinant of resistance to change at selected dealership companies in Durban, South Africa. Data were collected from 170 staff at selected dealership companies by means of questionnaire administration. The questionnaire (available on request from the authors) was designed and pre-tested to meet the specific aims of the research. It was applied to a sample of 170 staff across automobile dealership companies in Durban Metropolitan Region in August 2016. The first part of the questionnaire requested demographic data. The second part of the questionnaire posed 21 questions regarding change leadership styles (Transformational and Transactional Leadership styles). The third part of the questionnaire reflected on questions regarding respondents' behavior regarding resistance to change.

3.1 Research Design

A quantitative research approach following a descriptive research design was adopted in the study. Shuka (2008) noted that the quantitative research approach is associated with a cross-sectional survey and uses a descriptive research design.

3.2 Research Population and Sampling Process

According to Wellman and Kruger (2013), “the target population are several possible respondents that could be included in the research study. Hence, results obtained from the sample of the population can be used for a generalization of results”. Similarly, O’Leary (2014) defines a population as “the total membership of a defined class of people, objects, or events.” It is the full set of elements from which a sample is selected (Fox and Bayat, 2007).

The National Automobile Car Dealership Association (NADA) in South Africa reported about 660 automobile companies in South Africa, with 278 in the KwaZulu-Natal province and 35 companies in the Durban Metropolitan Region (NADA, 2015). However, further investigation by the researcher revealed the minimum number of employees found in any of these companies to be about 50 employees. Therefore, the number of employees in all the automobile dealership companies in the Durban metropolitan region would be approximately 1,750. The sample of the research is composed of selected dealership companies in the Durban Metropolitan Region in KwaZulu-Natal. The participants of the study consist of 270 employees. The returned response rate of questionnaires was approximately 60%. The study considered the questionnaire method and the convenience sampling method. The questionnaire form contains two measurement tools related to communication adequacy and resistance to change. The selected automotive dealership companies considered for this paper are located in the Durban Metropolitan Region in KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa. They comprise the following areas; Pinetown; Durban North; Hillcrest; Amanzitoti; Bluff; Umhlanga; Balito; Durban Central.

3.3 Questionnaire Development

The quantitative questionnaire comprised sections. First, the demographic data and the next section measuring the leadership styles construct comprised 19 items using the Multifactor Leadership questionnaire, while 17 items measuring resistance to change through the behaviour of respondents using the resistance to change scale questionnaire.

The selection of the sample size was non-random (purposive sampling) in order to fit the criteria used to identify the selected companies for research investigation. The unit of analysis comprised workers (managers and staff members) at the selected automobile dealership companies which were presently undergoing transformational changes. The workers were recruited due to their experiences in describing the internal information dissemination and communication between managers and subordinates.

3.4 Research Instrument Measures

The research instruments employed were as follows:

Multifactor leadership questionnaire:

Leadership styles in this study were based on the combination of an individual's beliefs, values, and preferences, as well as the organizational culture and norms which would encourage some styles and discourage others. It was operationalized by Avolio and Bass's (2004) Multifactor Leadership Questionnaire (MLQ), describing transactional and transformational styles. There were five general components of transformational leadership; (a) Idealized influence (attributed); (b) Charisma; (c) Inspirational motivation; (d) Intellectual stimulation; (e) Individualized consideration. The three general components of transactional leadership were (a) Contingent reward, (b) Active management-by-exception, (c) Passive management-by-exception.

Bass (1985) initially generated a total of 142 items describing transactional and transformational leaders through a literature search and an open-ended survey of 70 senior executives. The initial 142 items were reduced to a 73-item questionnaire by having a panel of 11 expert judges to determine whether an item represented either transactional or transformational leadership. Studies of the MLQ factor structure revealed that there were high, positive correlations among the four transformational leadership scales (Avolio and Bass, 2004; Barling; Howell and Avolio, 1993; Lievens, Geit, and Coetsier, 1997). However, Avolio and Bass (2004) and Howell and Avolio (1993) confirmed that these four factors composing transformational leadership were conceptually and empirically distinct.

Resistance to change scale

Resistance to change was conceptualized and operationalized in this study as an employee multidimensional disposition that comprises a "tri-dimensional" negative attitude towards change, including affective, behavioral, and cognitive components (Oreg, 2006:76). In this study, the RTC scale (Oreg, 2003) was used to examine an employee's tendency to resist or avoid making change.

3.5 Ethical Consideration

Ethical clearance and permission to conduct the research were obtained from the Faculty Research Ethics Committee. The purpose and aims of the study were communicated to all participating respondents. More so, all respondents were informed of the option to withdraw their input at any stage if they wish to do so.

4. ANALYTICAL FINDINGS

Analysis based on empirical findings

The empirical evidence for items of constructs for Transformational Leadership which are: ID1, ID2, ID3, IM1, IM2, IM3, IS1, IS2, IS3, ID1, ID2, ID3 all indicate consistency and good leading indicating no significant relationship with cognitive rigidity. On the other hand,

empirical evidence for Transactional leadership indicates that its constructs AME1, AME2, PME1, PME2, PME3 shows no significant relationship with cognitive rigidity except for contingent reward.

Table 1. Factor Loadings of Constructs

CONSTRUCTS/ ITEMS	MEASURED VARIABLES	FACTOR LOADINGS
IDEALISED INFLUENCE (IF1)	It feels good to work with my manager	0.880
IDEALISED INFLUENCE (IF2)	I am proud to be associated with my manager.	0.834
IDEALISED INFLUENCE (IF3)	My manager's values and beliefs are very impressive.	0.888
INSPIRATIONAL MOTIVATION (IM1)	I am encouraged to provide new ways of looking at things.	0.879
INSPIRATIONAL MOTIVATION (IM2)	I am compelled to understand the articulated vision of change.	0.899
INSPIRATIONAL MOTIVATION (IM3)	My manager enables me to seek views on problems	0.864
INTELLECTUAL STIMULATION (IS1)	I am encouraged to rethink ideas never questioned.	0.798
INTELLECTUAL STIMULATION (IS2)	I am aware and updated as to how I am coping with my job.	0.770
INTELLECTUAL STIMULATION (IS3)	Personal attention to staff feelings is considered	0.801
INTELLECTUAL STIMULATION (ID1)	Staff are told what to do if they want to be rewarded.	0.798
INTELLECTUAL STIMULATION (ID2)	Staff are subjected to reward recognition with goals reached	0.770
INTELLECTUAL STIMULATION (ID3)	Staff clarify their responsibility for target achievement.	0.801
ACTIVE MANAGEMENT BY EXCEPTION (AME1)	My manager is satisfied when I meet the agreed standard	0.719
ACTIVE MANAGEMENT BY EXCEPTION (AME2)	Staff are told the agreed standard and expectations in job delivery	0.751
PASSIVE MANAGEMENT BY EXCEPTION (PME1)	Nothing remains changed by the management if things are working well.	0.666
PASSIVE MANAGEMENT BY EXCEPTION (PME2)	The management is content with staff working in an unusual way as always	0.765
PASSIVE MANAGEMENT BY EXCEPTION (PME3)	Management is fine with whatever the staff wants to do.	0.831
CONTINGENT REWARD (CR1)	The management cares less about what staff does unless work is essential.	0.635
CONTINGENT REWARD (CR2)	My manager is satisfied when I meet the expected goals.	0.838

5. RESULTS

5.1 Socio-Demographic Characteristics

The gender distribution of staff per age group. The Fisher exact tests failed to show significant differences in gender with respect to the age distribution of the participants ($p > 0.05$). The males (57.6%) were slightly higher than the females (42.4%) participants. With regards to the age distribution, the proportion of males (5.3%) within the age distribution of 18-24 years old was higher than the females (4.7%). Similarly, males were more within the age distribution of 25-34 (25.9%) and 35-44 years old (15.9%), respectively. Equally, male (7.1%) participants constitute the highest number within the age distribution of 29-34 years old. However, within the age distribution of 55-64 years old, females (4.1%) were more than males (3.5%). Overall, more (47.8%) of the participants are within the age distribution of 25-34 years old with the lowest representative within the age distribution of 55-64 years old (7.6%).

The racial profile of the participants indicated 43 (25.3%) were African, 14 (8.2%) Coloured, 77 (45.3%) Indian, and 36 (21.2%) White. Overall, the Indian (45.3) participants were the majority with Coloured making up the lowest (8.2%) number of the participants in terms of their racial group.

It can be gathered that majority of the participants had a matric level of education (84.7%) while very few (0.6%) of the participants had education below matric.

5.2. Measurement Model

The proposed measurement model was tested using a structural equation model (SEM). This was carried out in two phases. In the first phase, the validity and reliability of the measurement model were established. The second phase entails testing the structural path model. At both stages, the model fit indices are found to test the constructs.

The structural equation model (SEM) was computed using Amos (IBM software) to identify the causal relationship between these change leadership styles (transformational and transactional) and cognitive rigidity as a construct of employee resistance to change

There are sets of criteria used to determine the model fit in SEM. The generated Chi-square value χ^2 , divided by df, and expressed as CMIN/DF, must be less than 5 (Atiku, 2014). The comparative fit index (CFI) is another determining value, which is a form of incremental fit index that measures the fit of the model. As a rule of thumb, the CFI value is recommended to be greater than 0.9 for the model to be considered a good fit (Kline, 2011). Another important measure of model fit is the root mean square error of approximation (RMSEA). For the RMSEA, a value that is less than 0.08 is recommended, which suggests an approximate fit (Hooper, 2008:54).

Figure 2: Model indicating the relationship between constructs

The figure above indicates the relationship between transformational and transactional leadership and cognitive rigidity and resistance to change. The Pearson correlation values reveal that a passive management leadership style correlates positively with cognitive rigidity ($r=0.313, p<0.001$). The association was found to be weak. However, no association was found between all the other constructs of transformational and transactional leadership and cognitive rigidity as a construct of resistance to change. The contingent reward construct was removed as it was not loading and as a result, could not fit into the model analysis. The values in the figure suggest that this model has a good fit in terms of validity and reliability.

5.3 Discriminant and Convergent Validity

	COGNITIVE RIGIDITY	AVE	MSV	MaxR(H)	IS	IF	IM	PME	AME	CR
IS	0.772	0.558	0.817	0.896	0.747					
IF	0.852	0.657	0.867	0.964	0.782	0.810				
IM	0.845	0.613	0.867	0.932	0.904	0.931	0.783			
PME	0.739	0.423	0.119	0.771	0.180	0.202	0.179	0.650		
AME	0.564	0.475	0.760	0.895	0.562	0.647	0.663	0.275	0.689	
CR	0.587	0.448	0.760	0.822	0.710	0.670	0.712	0.345	0.872	0.669

The values in the table above indicate that Idealised Influence, Inspirational motivation, Intellectual stimulation, Passive management by exception and active management by exception all have good reliability and are consistent which indicates a good discriminant and convergent validity. The Association between these leadership styles and cognitive rigidity as a construct of resistance to change using multiple regression analysis displayed correlation measures with the linear relationship between both variables, it does not imply a cause-and-effect relationship. Before performing the multi-regression analysis, the data were screened for the presence of collinearity as indicated in Table 2. According to Pallant (2016: 278),

collinearity can be diagnosed by checking the tolerance coefficient and variance inflation factor (VIF) values.

6. DISCUSSION

6.1 Perception of staff regarding Transformational Leadership Style

Transformational leaders are dynamic, energetic, compassionate leader who thrive and grow organizations as employees are in a supportive environment which encourages their initiatives and expression of individuality (Kahn and Aslam, 2012:18). According to Singh (2015:749), transformational leaders strategically reduce resistance levels and enhance job satisfaction.

Findings from the quantitative study revealed that 81 % of staff feels good to work with their managers and 80 % are proud to be associated to their manager while 78.8% also believe in the impressive values of their managers. It is concluded that in terms of idealized influence, a higher proportion or percentage of staff and managers agree with the practice of transformational leadership style. Regarding inspirational motivation, quantitative findings revealed that 81.2% of participants were encouraged by their managers to utilize their best skills to full capacity, which suggest that participants are confident in the commitment of their managers towards their work. Similarly, 75% of participants agreed to be assisted by managers to put meaning to work in congruence with change implementation and organizational goals. 77% of participants are compelled to understand the articulated vision of any change implementation. Revealed that 71.8% of participants agreed their managers enable them to think about old problems in new dimensions. Similarly, 73.5% also agreed that they were provided with new ways of looking at puzzling things. However, a lower percentage (35.3%) of participants agreed their ideas have never been questioned. In summary, staff perception suggests the practice of transformational leadership as it promotes intellectual creativity.

6.2 Perception of Staff regarding Transactional Leadership Style

A transactional leader rewards employees for task completion thereby attaining power from the transactions which allow followers to fulfil their own self-interest and concentrate on organizational goals to increase quality (Kahn and Gupta, 2016:158). A transactional leader is governed more by contractual agreements rather than trust (Kahn and Gupta, 2016:18). Empirical evidence from previous investigations supports the relationship between transactional leadership and effectiveness in some settings. However, findings from this study revealed a higher number of positive agreements regarding contingent rewards (85.3%), active management by exception (83.6%) and lesser percentage of staff agreement regarding passive management by exception (46%) to promote the influence of productivity amongst the employees just as pointed out by previous research investigations.

6.3 Impact of Transformational Leadership Style on Employee Resistance to Change

Previous findings from studies support that a significant relationship exists between transformational leadership and resistance to change (Hypothesis 1). Nielsen et al. (2008:468) revealed that transformational leadership was positively associated with better working

conditions. Prosci's model of change management also suggests that good working conditions lead to increased commitment to work.

Findings from this study reveal a negative correlation ($r= 0.480$) which suggests that as resistance to change increases, transformational leadership reduces and vice versa. This goes in line with the literature of various researchers which suggests and has proven that transformational leadership reduces resistance.

6.4 Impact of Transactional Leadership Style on Employee Resistance to Change.

Emery and Baker (2008:84) claim there is a significant correlation between transactional leadership and resistance to change (as proposed in Hypothesis 2) especially when the leader utilizes a wrong change management approach. Findings from this study reveal a linear relationship between resistance to change and transactional leadership in the surveyed companies which shows a negative correlation ($r= 0.365$) suggesting that as resistance to change increases, transactional leadership increases and vice versa. This correlation value is less than that of the transformational leadership style which implies that the transactional leadership style stands a better chance to increase resistance to change compared to the transformational leadership style just as suggested by other research findings.

7. PRACTICAL IMPLICATIONS

Arising from the empirical analysis of the findings, it is vital for managers to overcome resistance to make employees commit to the change without making them feel that the change is forced on them (De Jagger, 2010:112). Commitment to change is believed to be necessary for successful change management and managers should spend more time listening to staff to handle resistance. Furthermore, by setting a good example, managers have a great possibility to positively influence employees by taking into consideration employees' interests during the implementation; communicating with the employees in order to make them understand the meaning of change; trying out different leadership approaches in dealing with resistance because not all employees resist change in the same way; and finally, communicating with employees at all levels in the organization to achieve a successful change implementation (Strebel, 2010:113).

According to Singh (2015:749), a transformational leadership style strategically reduces resistance levels and enhances job satisfaction. Findings from the study also proved that as transformational leadership increases, resistance reduces and vice versa. On the other hand, the transactional leadership style is governed more by contractual agreements than trust (Kahn and Gupta, 2016:18) and indicated a linear relationship with resistance to change which simply means that as transactional leadership style increases, resistance to change increases and vice versa.

This suggests that the transformational leadership style will provide a more conducive environment for change management implementation compared to the transactional leadership style at the selected automobile dealership companies in DMR.

8. CONCLUSION

The study identified the importance of effective change management leadership in organizations undergoing some form of change in their operations to cope with modern existence. The result of the study suggests that staff participation and trust in management is very essential as well as communication flow between staff and management leaders. The comparison of transformational leadership against transactional leadership style emphasized the need for further practice of transformational leadership style which accounted for less resistance from the staff at the selected automobile dealership companies in the Durban Metropolitan Region of KwaZulu-Natal. Further studies could be carried out to include other factors which are not included in the study. Also, this research considered only the dealership automotive sector in a region of KwaZulu-Natal in South Africa. Other researchers may include multiple organizations in other geographical areas of South Africa.

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